

Regional landslide prediction: comparing open-access Digital Elevation Models to delineate slope units

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¹*Abstract*— Digital Elevation Models (DEMs) significantly influence landslide studies including detection and prediction. Often, DEM selection is based on accessibility and resolution rather than accuracy. This study compares freely available global DEMs (ALOS, COP, FABDEM) and a national DEM (TINITALY) against a reference DEM (airborne LiDAR) to determine the most suitable model for capturing fine-scale morphology and SU partitioning in the Marche Region of Italy to contribute towards landslide susceptibility studies. The evaluation considered multiple factors, including differences in elevation, residual DEMs, roughness indices, slope variations, and SU delineation capability. Among the tested models, TINITALY, resampled to a 30x30m resolution, proved most effective for representing detailed terrain morphology. It was subsequently used to generate the optimal SU partition from 18 different configurations. These combinations were assessed using existing and newly integrated metrics, using mapped polygonal landslide inventories.

I. INTRODUCTION

Freely accessible global Digital Elevation Models (DEMs) have been widely utilized for extensive geomorphological studies, which require modelling or analysis for mountainous terrains, where the DEMs accuracy is lower than in flat terrains [1], [2]. DEMs are commonly used in landslide modelling to predict and detect slope failures as well as derive terrain based characteristics where the accuracy is influenced by the quality and resolution of the DEM.

To assess the suitability of DEMs for landslide susceptibility and prediction, quality assessments have essentially been conducted. Therefore, global DSMs and a national Italian Digital Terrain Model (DTM) have been compared with a local high resolution (1m) elevation model (Airborne LiDAR) in the context

of terrain representation and its delineation, referred to as “reference DEM” in the following text. Once the most accurate DEM has been selected, it was used to delineate the optimal Slope Units (SUs) partition. The Marche region, shown in Figure 1, was selected to test the two approaches proposed. The study area AOIa represents the Marche region which was used in the second methodological phase of SU delineation, while AOIb is a subset of the Marche region which is equipped with the necessary information required to complete a DEM comparison.

Figure 1. Central Italy divided in two study areas. AOIa; used in the second phase of analyses representing the Marche region. AOIb; used in the first phase of analysis by comparing LiDAR with public DEMs. Adapted from [3]

Figure 2. Methodology described according to the two-phased analysis where Phase 1 involved DEM comparisons (AOIb) and Phase 2 is dedicated to SU delineations (AOIa). Adapted from [3].

I. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Phase 1: DEM assessment

The first phase (Figure 2) comprises of comparing global DEMs; Advanced Land Observing Satellite (ALOS) surveyed in 2006-2011, Copernicus Glo-30 (COP) from a mission of 2011-2015, Forest And Buildings removed Copernicus DEM (FABDEM), as well as the national Italian DEM TINITALY. These DEMs are compared with the reference DEM, which is an airborne LiDAR DTM at 1m resolution acquired in 2012 (<https://gn.mase.gov.it/portale/pst-dati-lidar>). The comparisons were made for the representation of fine-scale morphological characteristics such as roughness, slope and elevation in AOIb area.

B. Phase 2: Slope Unit delineation

Once the most suitable DEM has been identified, it was used to subdivide the AOIa area in SUs. Several combinations of input parameters have been compared to understand the most representative terrain partitioning (Figure 2). The software *r.slopeunits* [4] was used for SU generation and in particular two parameters were changed to create 18 combinations: the *minimum surface area* of SU (a) and the *minimum circular variance* for terrain (c). The combinations were evaluated by using three performance metrics: i) aspect segmentation (F) proposed by Alvioli et al. [4] that evaluates the segmentation based on internal homogeneity and external heterogeneity of SUs; ii) landslide density (D) which is representative of the mean number of landslides within a unstable terrain unit, signifying the use of landslide inventories to delineate SUs; iii) landslide extension (A) is the sum of the landslide areas contained within a SU respect to the total landslide areas. The product (S) of their normalized values ($\tilde{F}, \tilde{A}, \tilde{D}$), has been used to select the optimal SU delineation (Eq. 1).

$$S = \tilde{F} \cdot \tilde{A} \cdot \frac{1}{\tilde{D}} \quad (1)$$

These metrics have been introduced in this study as a new approach to integrate landslide polygons in terrain partitioning for landslide susceptibility modelling.

II. RESULTS

The differences in elevation, slope, isotropic roughness, radial roughness and residual elevation between the DEMs and the reference DEM are reported in Figure 3.

A notable observation is the similarity between COP and FABDEM. Since FABDEM (a DTM) is an improvement of a DSM (COP), it should theoretically provide a more accurate representation of the terrain, making it similar to the LiDAR reference. However, FABDEM does not exhibit smaller differences in comparison to COP when compared with the reference DEM. This can be explained by the motivation of FABDEM construction being for flood modelling [5]. Thus, the application of a DTM generated for hydrogeomorphology purposes may not perform strongly in applications of slope instability.

TINITALY10m and TINITALY30m were also compared with their respective resolutions to the LiDAR as shown in Figure 4. TINITALY30m shows lower differences across the metrics used. At the conclusion of Phase 1 the resampled 30m TINITALY DEM is the most suitable choice for SU delineation in the Marche region conducted within the Phase 2.

SU delineations were tested across a combination of parameters (18 combinations) and tested with F, A and D metrics, summarized in the S metric as shown in Table 1. The higher the S value, the better the SU representation is considered. The behavior of combinations shows that extreme values (low c and a , and high c and a) almost nullifies the S metric value since the SU are represented out of proportion.

Table 1. S metric values for corresponding parameters of 18 SU combinations. Adapted from [3].

S	Minimum surface area (a) m ²					
	40000	80000	150000	200000	300000	500000
Circular variance (c)						
0.1	0	0.048	0.243	0.301	0.317	0.005
0.4	0.087	0.087	0.083	0.080	0.028	0.014
0.7	8.17×10^{-5}	8.17×10^{-5}	6.91×10^{-5}	9.73×10^{-5}	3.26×10^{-5}	0

Figure 3. Boxplots showing the differences in metrics used to describe fine-scale morphology using the global/national DEMs and the reference DEM (30m). The metrics represented are; A) Elevation, B) Slope, C) Isotropic Roughness Index, D) Radial Roughness Index and E) Residual DEM. Adapted from [3].

I. DISCUSSION

A comparison of global DEMs and the resampled 30m TINITALY against the reference airborne LiDAR DEM (resampled to 30m to match the resolution) revealed significant differences in selected geomorphometric derivatives within AOIb. While TINITALY 30m performs better against all other DEMs, it is also interesting to observe the low performance of TINITALY 10m. This can signify that areas of low-sampling density generate artifacts which are smoothed while upscaling the DEM and thus, affects the geomorphometric derivatives. Figure 5 also shows the visual differences in slope where TINITALY30m variates the least with the reference DEM and became an ideal choice to test SU parameters.

Figure 4. Boxplots depicting the differences in TINITALY at 10m and 30m against the reference DEM. The metrics represented are; A) Elevation, B) Slope, C) Isotropic Roughness Index, D) Radial Roughness Index and E) Residual DEM. Adapted from [3].

To assess the impact of terrain partitioning on the landslide susceptibility model, both the best SU partition ($c = 0.1$ and $a = 300 \times 10^3 \text{ m}^2$) and worst case ($c = 0.7$ and $a = 150 \times 10^3 \text{ m}^2$) landslide susceptibility scenarios were analyzed using a Generalized Additive Model. Notably, performance metrics such as Area Under the Curve (AUC), F1 score (F1), and Cohen's Kappa Index (Kappa) exhibited trends opposite to those of the S metric, indicating that higher S metric performance does not necessarily correspond to a better susceptibility model performance. This is a well-known behavior related to the smoothing effect of large SU on the explanatory variables which is represented by a single value per SU.

Future research should explore multi-temporal SU delineations using space-time inventories. Adapting SU delineation to evolving terrains, could significantly enhance landslide prediction accuracy.

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Figure 5. Mapped differences in slope (degrees) between the tested DEMs (30m) and the reference DEM, in a local zoom in of AOIb. Adapted from [3].

II. CONCLUSIONS

This study evaluates global and national DEMs for their ability to derive fine-scale terrain features. Among the tested DEMs (ALOS, COP, FABDEM, TINITALY), TINITALY30m showed superior performance and was used to generate optimized SU partitions.

Moreover, a new method to assess SU configurations based on internal homogeneity, external heterogeneity, landslide presence and landslide area has been proposed. Results show that terrain partitioning influences susceptibility modeling, though model performance metrics (AUC, F1, Kappa) don't always align with SU quality.